

Fabrication and characterization of LM-TENG for Energy Harvesting and Sensors Applications

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ABSTRACT

Triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) are playing vital role for energy harvesting and self-powered devices since 2012 [1]. These TENGs operate in different modes using variety of materials such as solid-solid, solid-liquid, and liquid-liquid. In this paper we are introducing an efficient solid-liquid TENG for energy harvesting and self-powered sensors. Here we used free standing mode where liquid metal (Hg) is used to transfer charge on triboelectric layer. This TENG is fabricated by sticking two electrodes (Al or Cu) on acrylic substrate whereas kapton, PDMS, and PTFE is deposited on its top which serve as triboelectric layer. This liquid metal (LM) based TENG is fabricated in variety of shapes such as planer, channel, and tubular. In each shape it is sensitive to Hg flow on its surface for producing electrical signals. As compare to other liquids Hg does not adsorb on kapton, PDMS or PTFE surface giving hydrophobic behavior. In each shape the LM-TENG is sensitive to Hg flow on its surface for producing electrical signals. For a single drop of Hg the fabricated LM-TENG produced maximum V_{pp} of 16V. This LM-TENG has been used as self-powered sensor to detect the position, distance and speed of Hg drop passing on its surface,

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important issues facing contemporary science and technology is the growing need for portable and sustainable energy sources. The Internet of Things (IoT), wearable technology, biomedical implants, and wireless sensors are all growing at a rapid pace. As a result, there is an urgent demand for flexible, lightweight, and eco-friendly miniature power supply. Although they offer short-term fixes, conventional power sources like electrochemical batteries and super capacitors have intrinsic disadvantages such short lifespans, frequent replacement, environmental

risks, and incompatibility with flexible and deformable electronics [2] Similar to this, traditional energy harvesters like electromagnetic generators (EMGs) are inappropriate for low-frequency and small-scale energy harvesting applications because they need high-frequency mechanical motion and large-scale systems to provide efficient output. Even though they are effective on a broad scale, renewable energy technologies like solar cells and wind turbines are still very dependent on the environment and cannot produce steady outputs for portable or implanted devices. Rather than that, the traditional energy sources were not clean and was

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the rising concern over the global warming [4]. These drawbacks show how urgently a scalable, adaptable, and ecologically safe alternative self-powered energy source is needed. In this regard, the triboelectric Nanogenerator (TENG), which was initially presented by Wang and associates in 2012 [3], has become a ground-breaking device for producing electricity from mechanical energy [3], TENGs function on the basis triboelectrification and electrostatic induction, in which these charges propel electron flow in external circuits, and triboelectrification, [5] which is the creation of surface charges through contact or friction between two dissimilar materials. TENGs are particularly useful for biomechanical energy harvesting from human walking,[6] joint movement, vibrations, water waves,[7] and other environmental motions because they can efficiently harvest low-frequency mechanical energy (<5 Hz), in contrast to EMGs, which are only effective at frequencies above 50 Hz.(3) TENGs have drawn a lot of interest for powering small-scale electronics and enabling the idea of self-powered systems because of its straightforward construction, lightweight design, variety of materials, and high energy conversion efficiency[8]. Contact-separation (CS), lateral sliding (LS), single-electrode (SE), and freestanding triboelectric-layer (FS) modes are the four basic operation modes of TENGs that have been developed since their development to maximize energy harvesting efficiency. For instance, CS mode offers a straightforward structure but suffers from surface wear; LS mode minimizes wear through shear motion; SE mode permits compact device design by connecting a single electrode to the load; and FS mode permits scalable, non-contact designs appropriate for environmental energy harvesting. These adaptable architectures have made it possible for TENGs to be used in a variety of fields, from blue energy harvesting from ocean waves to wearable electronics and self-powered sensors. However, the majority of early TENG research has focused on solid–solid interfaces, which, although effective, suffer from challenges such as incomplete surface contact, mechanical wear, durability issues, and sensitivity to environmental humidity. [9]. Researchers have turned their attention to solid–liquid and liquid–dielectric interface TENGs in order to get over these restrictions. Liquids provide closer contact with solid surfaces, improved charge transfer, and less mechanical wear because of their intrinsic fluidity and deformability [10]. For instance, metallic conductivity, deformability, and self-healing properties are provided by liquid-metal-based TENGs made of materials like eutectic gallium–indium (EGaIn), which lead to increased charge density and enhanced durability [11]. However, in order to create stretchable and biocompatible TENGs appropriate for wearable and implantable devices, ionic solutions and

hydrogels have been investigated as liquid dielectrics. Small gadgets like fitness trackers, watches, and health monitors can be powered by these systems, which can capture biomechanical energy from routine human actions like walking, bending joints, and hand movements. However, the long-term stability of ionic-solution-based TENGs is limited by issues such low conductivity, water evaporation, and wetting-induced charge loss.

Super hydrophobic modifications, usually accomplished through micro/Nano structuring combined with low-surface-energy coatings like fluorinated silanes or PDMS, provide water contact angles exceeding 150°. These surfaces enable faster droplet rolling, reduced adhesion forces, and efficient charge transfer, thereby improving output performance and durability [12]. Such TENG showed that super hydrophobic PDMS and PTFE surfaces increased droplet velocity by 200% when compared to hydrophilic surfaces. A. Additionally, ultra-hydrophobic coatings prolong the operational lifetimes of TENGs from hundreds to thousands of cycles by shielding them against corrosion, swelling, and hydrolysis) Despite these benefits, ultra-hydrophobic surfaces may also create air pockets at the interface that serve as lubricants and lower charge density, resulting in a trade-off between efficiency and repellency.

Liquid-dielectric TENGs have developed into extremely stretchy and shape-adaptive devices in recent years [13]. For instance, a TENG that can sustain 300% strain while maintaining steady function by encasing salt chloride solution in silicone rubber. By creating hydrogel-based TENGs with stretchability above 1100% and stable functioning under changing humidity and temperature, expanded this idea. Self-healing TENGs that can recover from mechanical damage [14], however they noted a notable loss in performance when hydrophobic surfaces deteriorated under water exposure. A. These developments show the promise of liquid-based systems for biomedical and wearable electronics of the future, but they also draw attention to outstanding problems such surface degradation, evaporation instability, conductivity restrictions, and fabrication complexity.

The field of liquid-based TENGs still has a number of research gaps despite its quick advancement. In contrast to liquid metals, which are extremely conductive but constrained by toxicity, weight, and expense, the majority of ionic-solution devices still have conductivity issues. Device effectiveness is still decreased by wetting and surface deterioration, and existing super hydrophobic techniques, although successful, are difficult to produce on a large scale and deteriorate with time. Moreover, the trade-off between output efficiency, stability, and adaptability is still unresolved. A. New materials and designs that combine the stretch ability, biocompatibility, and low-cost benefits of

ionic solutions with the conductivity and durability of liquid metals are therefore desperately needed. High-performance, long-lasting, and adaptable TENGs for practical applications may be possible through the use of hybrid materials, sophisticated encapsulation techniques, and strong super hydrophobic engineering.

Here in this paper we are introducing three types of liquid-solid TENGs which work in free standing mode and Hg is used as working fluid which transfers charges effectively between two electrodes.

MATERIALS

SYLGARD 184 Silicone Elastomer and curing agent from USA, Cu sticking tape for Alibaba, Al sticking tape from Alibaba, acrylic sheet, mercury, kapton sticking tape from Alibaba, PTFE sticking tape from Alibaba.

METHOD

Three types of LM-TENGs were fabricated in free standing mode using kapton, PDMS and PTFE as triboelectric layers in planer, channel and tubular shapes respectively.

Planer LM-TENG: The schematic of fabrication steps for planer TENG is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of fabrication steps of planer LM-TENG

An acrylic sheet of 0.3cm, 15cm, 20cm thickness, width and length respectively was used as substrate. 14 pairs of Cu electrodes were pasted in comb configuration where each electrode was 50 μ m thick and its width was 3.5mm. The average distance between electrodes was 2mm. The kapton tape was pasted on top of electrodes which serve as triboelectric layer. The thickness of kapton tape was 100 μ m. For electrical characterization Hg drops were continuously dropped on TENG surface with same sequence and all of the Hg was collected back in a beaker.

Micro structured PDMS Channel: The schematic of fabrication steps of microstructured PDMS channel TENG is shown in figure 2. Three pair electrodes were pasted on a glass substrate. The glass substrate was then given a boundary (using Al tape). Next the cavity was filled with

PDMS. The PDMS was prepared from 10:1 silicone elastomer and curing agent respectively. A template containing micro mashed structure and channel structure was inserted in cavity containing PDMS. Finally, the PDMS was bubbled in vacuum and harden using temperature treatment. The template was peel off and the boundary was also removed which result a channel having microstructured PDMS at its bottom.

Figure 2: Fabrication steps for making microstructured PDMS channel LM-TENG

Tubular LM-TENG: For making tubular TENG a PTFE tube of 0.4cm inner diameter and 0.6cm out diameter was used. Four pairs of Cu electrodes were pasted on outer surface of PTFE tube.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three types of LM TENGs were fabricated using kapton, PDMS and PTFE as triboelectric layer in planer, channel and tubular shape respectively. In each TENG Hg was used as working fluid transferring charges between two electrodes.

i. Planer LM-TENG

The Digital camera image of fabricated LM-TENG is shown in Figure 3. It consists of acrylic base, Cu electrodes, and kapton insulating (triboelectric) layer. This TENG is used in free standing mode where 14 pairs of adjacent electrodes are covered with triboelectric layer. All electrodes combine together in pairs making a comb like structure. Here kapton is used as triboelectric layer which is pasted on two Cu electrodes. The liquid metal mercury is used as working fluid to carry charges between two electrodes. Mercury has two main advantages in TENG as it is good charge carrier and gives hydrophobic behavior on kapton surface.

Figure 3: Digital camera image of kapton based planer LM-TENG.

The electrical characterization of LM-TENG is shown in figure 4. For electrical characterization the comb electrodes are connected with NI data acquisition card which send the generated signals to computer and store in the form of data. The LM –TENG is placed at 45° and Hg drops are continuously dropped on its surface. When a drop of Hg passes on the surface of kapton the TENG generates 14 pulses which actually represent the passage of drop from each pair of electrodes as shown in Figure 4(c). Similarly when number of drops flow on TENG surface it generates number of energy packets as shown in Figure 4(a,b). Where each packet consists of 14 pulses as explain in Figure 4 (c). Vpp of each pulse is approximately 16V. The analysis of these signals gives very interesting sensing parameters such as: in Figure 4(a) the total time is 28 sec and there are 24 packets. Accordingly, the drop frequency is 0.86 Hz. Similarly, each packet in figure represents a drop passing from top to bottom of TENG. The time for each packet is 0.2 sec as shown in figure 4(c). The distance from top to bottom electrode is 13cm. Hence the speed of drop is $13/0.2=65\text{cm/sec}$. In same way from peak values of each pulse in figure 4(c) the distance between each electrode can be calculated. From this discussion it is clear that, this type of TENG can be used as self-powered sensor for measuring frequency, speed and distance.

The LM-TENG has an advantage that from a single drop number of pulses are generated depending of number of electrodes. This TENG has number of applications as given below

Figure 4: Electrical signals generated from planer LM-TENG. a) pulses recorded for 28 seconds, b) magnifying a portion of pulses showing packet of pulses, c) focusing a single packet where 14 pulses represents the Hg drop passing from 14 pairs of electrodes in LM-TENG.

- 1) If such a TENG is encapsulated in a box filling few drops of mercury inside, then shaking it continuously generates enough amount of energy. Such a system may be placed in ocean to generate energy from waves.
- 2) If such a TENG is built in Circular tube filling few of ml mercury inside, then this tube will generate continues energy on rotating it. Such a TENG can be integrate in wheel of a vehicle there it can be used both for energy harvesting and sensing vehicle speed.
- 3) This TENG may be implemented in number of self-powered rotation, speed, distance, acceleration sensors and gyroscope.

ii. Microstructured channel LM-TENG

The digital camera and microscope images of fabricated PDMS microstructured LM-TENG is shown in figure 5. It has 10cm long PDMS channel which has 3mm width and 2mm height as shown in figure 5(a,b). The channel is decorated with microstructured PDMS domes as shown in figure 5(c). This microstructure was fabricated to enhance the total surface area of and output voltage. The electrodes are arranged in three pairs beneath PDMS microstructure. For electrical characterization the channel is placed at 45° and Hg drops are continuously dropped in channel. The electrical output of given TENG is shown in figure 6. Figure 6 (a) depicts the output for 35 seconds where 25 packets of pulses are generated which shows that Hg drop frequency is $25/35=0.71$ Hz. These packets are focused in figure 5(b) which consists of number of pulses. Figure 5(c) focuses a single packet which shows three major pulses. These pulses represent the passage of Hg drop passing from each pair of electrodes. Though these pulses are very clear, but the output voltage is very low.

Figure 5: Digital camera and microscope images of channel shaped LM-TENG a) Image showing channel shaped PDMS LM-TENG, b) magnified image c) optical microscope image focusing the micro domes in PDMS channel.

In this case the maximum V_{pp} is 0.35V which is much less compare to planer LM-TENG. One of the reasons of this low voltage is the hydrophobic behavior of Hg on PDMS surface. While passing from Channel the Hg only make contact with upper tips of domes which gives a small fraction of total surface area. In contrast in contact separation mode the same dome structure gives high voltage because there most of its area contributes in contact electrification.

Figure 6: Electrical characterization of channel shaped LM-TENG

Figure 7: Camera image of PTFE tubular LM-TENG

The electrical signal generated from this LM-TENG is shown in Figure 8. Figure 8(a) shows the electrical output recorded for 25 seconds where the Hg was moving in tube in forward and reverse direction. In each cycle the TENG was generating two packets of electrical signals. The variation in height and shape of these packets is due to manual moving of Hg where speed was not constant. Figure 8(b) shows that each packet of signal consist of number of pulses. Figure 8(c) focus a single packet and it can be observed that it consists of five major pulses which represents the passage of Hg from five pairs of electrodes. The average V_{pp} recorded in these signals are 8V

Figure 8. Electrical characterization of tubular LM-TENG

Three types of solid-liquid TENGs have been introduced. In each type liquid metal Hg is used as working fluid. Each of the fabricated TENG is capable of producing reasonable output at frequency of less than 1Hz. The planer LM-TENG proved to be good sensor for sensing drop frequency, speed, and distance covered on TENG surface. Microstructure on LM-TENG surface gives an adverse effect of producing lower voltage where only the tips of microstructure contributes in triboelectrification which is a small fraction of total surface area. This effect is in contrast to that of solid TENG in contact separation mode. The tubular LM-TENG is much productive in producing high voltage from very small quantity of Hg due to higher contact area. In each type of these LM-TENGs the Hg drop produces voltage pulse passing from any pair of electrodes.

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